

Distributed large MIMO Systems and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces in 6G –

with highlights from the Hexa-X and RISE-6G projects

Tommy Svensson

Full Professor, PhD, Leader Wireless Systems

Department of Electrical Engineering, Communication Systems Group

Chalmers University of Technology

tommy.svensson@chalmers.se

10.5281/zenodo.14188840

CHALMERS

March 29, 2023

Outline

- Mobile networks evolution 4G, 5G towards 6G
- From CoMP to Cell free Distributed large MIMO (D-MIMO)
- Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs)
- Take home messages

4th->5th Generation Mobile Communications (5G)

4G: Internet -> Mobile Internet with Rich multimedia

5G: Densification, mm-wave spectrum

=> **High speed/ high capacity mobile Internet**

Source: <https://marketingland.com/global-basis-mobile-internet-usage-surpassed-desktop-october-196937>

5G: Massive machine type communications

=> **Internet of Things**

Source: <https://www.aeteurope.com/news/technologies-secure-internet-things/>

5G: Robustness, Low latency

=> **Internet of Skills**

*Still work to be done
in 5G evolution*

Source: <https://www.einride.tech/press/>

Source: <https://www.tu-auto.com/phantom-auto-connects-spooked-cars-to-remote-drivers/>

Source: <https://www.ericsson.com/thinkingahead/the-networked-society-blog/2017/02/14/virtual-reality-comes-age-internet-skills/>

6th Generation Mobile Communications (6G)?

6G: Convergence of Digital, Human and Physical part of our world

Trustworthiness, Digital inclusion, Sustainable
-> Internet for Societal needs & UN Sustainability Goals

Source: Hexa-X deliverable D1.1 "6G Vision, use cases and key societal values", Feb 2021. Online: <https://hexa-x.eu/deliverables/>

Source: <https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/envision2030.html>

Source: Hexa-X deliverable D1.1 "6G Vision, use cases and key societal values", Feb 2021. Online: <https://hexa-x.eu/deliverables/>

Convergence of Communications, Sensing, and Computing & Storage with Artificial Intelligence (AI)
-> Internet of Senses
enabling authentic remote participation and interaction

Source: <https://www.geekwire.com/2016/microsoft-research-stars-wars-holoportation-hololens/>

Source: <https://towardsdatascience.com/ai-the-future-of-technology-and-the-world-86f59d0ef720>

Communications Systems group at Chalmers University of Technology

Impacts Wireless Standards: 3G, 4G, 5G, 6G, ...

<https://hexa-x.eu/>

<https://5g-ppp.eu/rise-6g/>

<https://5g-ppp.eu/5gcar>

<https://5g-mmagic.eu>

<https://www.metis2020.eu>

<https://ict-artist4g.eu>

<http://projects.celtic-initiative.org/winner+>

<http://cordis.europa.eu/infowin/acts/rus/projects/ac090.htm>

Hexa-X overview

- European 6G flagship research project
- 2.5 y long, started Jan 2021
- Funded through EU H2020 ICT-52
- 25 partners
 - NW vendors
 - Operators
 - Industry
 - Academia
 - SMEs
- Nokia is Project leader
- Ericsson is Technical manager

<https://hexa-x.eu/>

Hexa-X use cases

6G use case families

Representative use cases

Addressing extreme performance

- For Radio research Hexa-X focuses resources on upper mmW (100-300 GHz)
- Lower bands will be essential for coverage but may reuse 5G NR PHY
- Rest of project are mostly frequency-agnostic – solutions should be valid for all ranges (0-300 GHz)

Co-existence with legacy technology

Smooth migration to 6G capabilities

Local spectrum licenses

Enabling new use cases

*upper mmW is sometimes known as: “THz” or “sub-THz”. In Hexa-X the preferred term is upper mmW

Reimagining purpose of radio connection

Joint communication and sensing

Sensing functionality as an integrated part of the communication network

- Low-cost introduction of sensing functionality
- Benefit from huge number of network nodes ⇒ Enhanced sensing capabilities

To enable new and enhanced services
To enhance the network performance

From CoMP to Cell free Large D-MIMO

B4G

Source: ARTIST4G

6G(?)

5G/B5G

Source: mmMAGIC

With RIS(?)

Downlink CoMP Approaches and Algorithms

- Coordinated scheduling and/or beamforming
 - Data to a single user is transmitted from *one* of point
 - Scheduling decisions are coordinated
 - Requires exchange of *control data only*
- Coordinated joint processing/transmission
 - Data to a single user is simultaneously transmitted from *multiple* points
 - Alternatively using dynamic multipoint
 - Requires exchange of *user data as well*

Coordinated Multi-Point (CoMP)

Coordinated Multi-Point transmission (CoMP):

- Coordinated [scheduling/beamforming](#) over multiple cells has the potential to lower the interference levels in a frequency reuse one system
- Coordinated [multi-cell transmission and reception](#) has the potential to improve the outage capacity and to smoothen the capacity over the cell areas.

Conventional LTE system

System with ARTIST4G techniques (e.g. interference management)

System with ARTIST4G techniques (e.g. advanced relaying)

Attenuation at mm-wave Frequencies

Average atmospheric absorption of MMWs: (A) Sea Level: $T = 20^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P = 760\text{mm}$, $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 7.5 \text{ g/m}^3$ (B) 4 km altitude: $T = 0^{\circ}\text{C}$ $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 1 \text{ g/m}^3$

Source: Microwave Journal: http://www.microwavejournal.com/legacy_assets/FigureImg/AR_4772_Fig02_L.jpg

Coverage and Throughput Prediction at 60 GHz mm-wave using Ray Tracing

- Left: Path-loss with respect to distance for mm-wave outdoor system
Right: Throughput estimation using 17 BSs [ABA+15].
- *D5.1 "Initial multi-node and antenna transmitter and receiver architectures and schemes" March 2016, <https://5g-mmmagic.eu>*
- [ABA+15]: Abdullah, N.F.; Berraki, D.; Ameen, A.; Armour, S.; Doufexi, A.; Nix, A.; Beach, M., "Channel Parameters and Throughput Predictions for mmWave and LTE-A Networks in Urban Environments," in *Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC Spring), 2015 IEEE 81st*, vol., no., pp.1-5, 11-14 May 2015

Massive MIMO at Both Tx, Rx (MMIMMO)

scenario 1: communicating buildings, **N=512, f=30.72GHz**

scenario 3: communicating laptops, **N=32, f=76.8GHz**

scenario 2: communicating lamp posts (these are heights and separations in France), **N=256, f=42.7GHz**

scenario 4: side-to-side communicating cars (non moving), **N=256, f=38.4GHz**

scenario 5: communicating laptop-screen, **N=512, f=61.4GHz**

Legend:
..... Uniform linear antenna array

Friis transmission equation

$$P_{RX} = P_{TX} G_{TX} G_{RX} \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi r} \right)^2$$

Labels in the diagram:
 - P_{RX} : received power
 - P_{TX} : transmit power
 - G_{TX} and G_{RX} : gain of transmit and receive antennas
 - λ : wavelength
 - r : separation distance
 - The term $\left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi r} \right)^2$ is circled in red and labeled "Free space path loss".

Hundreds of bits/s/Hz possible using "Block Discrete Fourier Transform based Spatial Multiplexing with Maximum Ratio Transmission" (B-DFT-SM-MRT)

D.-T. Phan-Huy, P. Ratajczak, R. D'Errico, A. Clemente, J. Järveläinen, D. Kong, K. Haneda, B. Bulut, A. Karttunen, M. Beach, E. Mellios, M. Castaneda, M. Hunukumbure, T. Svensson, "Massive Multiple Input Massive Multiple Output for 5G Wireless Backhauling", IEEE Globecom'2017 ET5GB workshop.

Source: D5.1 "Initial multi-node and antenna transmitter and receiver architectures and schemes" March 2016, <https://5g-mmmagic.eu>

D-MIMO radio architecture studies

Potential benefits with D-MIMO:

- Mitigate unreliable links due to shadowing/blockage thanks to macro diversity.
- Further densification of APs for increased and consistent area capacity.
- Achieve sufficient link margin despite output power limitations and high pathloss at upper mmW and (sub-)THz frequencies.
- Allows for lowering the EIRP, which simplifies deployment.

Recent results on key technical components in D2.2:

- Analog centralized beamforming
- Distributed digital beamforming
- Integrated access and backhauling

D-MIMO radio architecture studies

D2.2 Contributions on D-MIMO:

- Challenges and opportunities with D-MIMO and its potential role in 6G
- The different challenges at lower and upper mmW/THz bands were highlighted, calling for a scalable approach from digital to analog approaches.
- Emphasized the need for efficient backhaul fronthaul solutions by integrating fibre and in-band wireless solutions.

Wide bandwidth D-MIMO system implemented using AroF and WDM.

Spectral efficiency for collocated ($L = 1$), partially ($L = \{4, 16\}$) and fully distributed ($L = 64$) interference aware distributed zero-forcing for different operating frequencies with cluster sizes $N_k = \{1, 4, 64\}$.

Comparison of power efficiency of optimized fully digital, and fully/partly connected hybrid beamforming (FDP/FHP/PHP), with/without silence mode activated vs node density.

Service coverage probability as a function of percentage of fractional fibre-backed small cell base stations for IAB.

Conclusions

- Densification key enabler to meet coverage and reliability targets at higher frequency bands – there seems to be sufficient spectrum available.
- Thus, low-cost solutions are more important than spectral efficiency, at least in the early roll-out phases.
- In the lower mmW bands the need for higher spectral efficiency calls for digital less distributed approaches.

Sustainable design – Design for Sufficiency

Energy Minimization under Service Constraints in mm-wave Multi-AP Cooperation

Jointly optimize

- Precoding
- Load balancing
- BS operation mode

To minimize network energy efficiency.

- Multiple base stations (BSs) jointly serving users to mitigate blocking and load balancing in dense mm-wave networks (standalone mm-wave BSs/ non-standalone, macro-BS assisted)
- Derive (close to) optimal fully digital- (FDB) and hybrid beamforming (HB) schemes.
- Minimize sum power *subject to per-user spectral efficiency constraints* and per BS peak power constraints, considering both hardware and RF transmit power of sleep mode capable BSs.

Sum RF transmit power and sum total power of all BSs

BS activation probability vs number of cooperative BSs

- [1] C. Fang, B. Makki, J. Li, T. Svensson, "Coordinated Hybrid Precoding for Energy-efficient Millimeter Wave Systems", SPAWC'2018. Invited paper.
- [2] C. Fang, B. Makki, J. Li, T. Svensson, "Hybrid Precoding in Cooperative Millimeter Wave Networks," in IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 20, no. 8, pp. 5373-5388, Aug. 2021.

Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB)

Arguments for IAB

- Network resources flexibility
- Network cost reduction
- Time-to-market reduction
- Controlled interference also in the backhaul/fronthaul

System model

Node/BS Distribution

- Finite homogeneous poisson point processes (FHPPP) for macro BS density (λ_M), small BS density (λ_S), blockers (λ_B) and users (λ_U).
- Two-tier HetNet on a circular plane

Blocking model

- Germ grain model
- OpenStreetMap 3D

Rain model: ITU-R Rec 8.38-3

IAB nodes density providing same coverage probability as fiber-backhauling

- Simulation parameters: $(\alpha_{LOS}; \alpha_{NLOS}) = (2; 3)$, blocker lengths $l_B = 5 \text{ m}$, $f_c = 28 \text{ GHz}$, bandwidth=1 GHz and $P_{MBS}; P_{SBS}; P_{UE} = (40; 24; 0) \text{ dBm}$.

Service coverage probability as a function of percentage of fiber-backhauled SBSs

- Simulation parameters: $(\alpha_{LOS}; \alpha_{NLOS}) = (2; 3)$, blocker lengths $l_B = 5 \text{ m}$, $f_c = 28 \text{ GHz}$, bandwidth= 1 GHz and $P_{MBS}; P_{SBS}; P_{UE} = (40; 24; 0) \text{ dBm}$.

D2.1 Large D-MIMO Gap Analysis

Research on distributed large MIMO systems for Beyond 5G/6G are still needed to be conducted in several areas

- Scalability for availability, such as distributed joint precoder/decoder design without CSI exchange
- Precoding schemes (especially for the upper mmW bands) including joint multi-tx/multi-rx with HW and backhaul-fronthaul constraints awareness
- Precoding (and other resource allocation) schemes in case of multi-antenna UEs
- UE beamforming
- 3D cell-free massive MIMO systems employing vertical coordination/cooperation
- Wireless mesh networking in converged backhaul/fronthaul and access for reliability
- IAB in cell-free massive MIMO, including full duplex
- Converged IAB for cell-free massive MIMO, in which nodes can act as both access and backhaul nodes
- Cell-free massive MIMO using (sub-)THz bands for backhaul/fronthauling, access and joint access/backhaul/fronthauling
- Heterogeneous spectrum use in cell-free massive MIMO systems, in which lower bands are used to assist and coordinate access/backhaul/fronthauling at higher bands
- Distributed large MIMO systems using Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS)
- Interference handling in integrated access backhaul and pure fronthaul in mesh configurations operating beyond 100 GHz using beamforming/MIMO
- Dynamic blocking mitigation in mmW bands, enabled e.g. by location and mapping information
- Mobility support in cell-free massive MIMO systems

Impact on End-to-end Architecture

1: Exposure of capabilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> E.g., Analytics information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Predictable latency, predicting future performance of a connection, etc. 	2: Designed for automation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Full closed-loop automation support Possible to utilise distributed AI/ML agents 	3: Extensibility and flexibility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapt to scenarios such as new private networks, autonomous networks, mesh networks, new spectrum, etc.
4: Scalability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support very small to very large-scale deployments dynamically 	5: Resilience and availability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using multi connectivity and separation of CP and UP Support of local network survivability in case a subnetwork loses connectivity with another network 	6: Exposed interfaces are service based <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network interfaces should be designed to be cloud native Easy to add new services to the network
7: Separation of concerns of network functions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimal dependency between network functions => network functions can be developed and replaced independently from each other. 		8: Network simplification in comparison to previous generations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce complexity utilising a cloud-native RAN and CN functions with fewer parameters to configure.

- D-MIMO impact on E2E Network Architecture in relation to the Architectural principles 1-8:
 - Extensibility and flexibility
 - Scalability
 - Resilience and availability
 - Separation of concerns of network functions

- Details can be found in D1.3 Sec. 3.2.2 Distributed Large MIMO

https://hexa-x.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Hexa-X_D1.3.pdf

Potential of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) in mm-wave Systems

- Fundamentally, RIS is a special case of D-MIMO, however
 - RISs can potentially accommodate much more radio elements than antenna arrays
 - Be deployed in new places and by other actors

- Sufficient number of RIS elements are needed for an overall gain

The effect of the # of RIS elements N on the received SNR with the optimum phase shifts at the RIS.

S. M. Razavizadeh, T. Svensson, "3D Beamforming in Intelligent Reconfigurable Surface-assisted Wireless Communication Networks", WSA'2020.

Other potential benefits (ongoing work):

- Dynamic blockage avoidance

H. Guo, B. Makki, M. Åström, M.-S. Alouini, and T. Svensson, "Dynamic blockage pre-avoidance using reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," submitted to IEEE Communications Magazine, 2022.

- Electromagnetic Field Exposure Avoidance

H. Guo, D. -T. Phan-Huy, and T. Svensson, "Electromagnetic Field Exposure Avoidance thanks to Non-Intended User Equipment and RIS," IEEE GLOBECOM Workshop, Dec. 2022.

RISE-6G

Reconfigurable Intelligent Sustainable Environments for 6G Wireless Networks

Coordinator: CEA-LETI
Duration: Jan 2021-Dec 2023

<https://rise-6g.eu>

The Potential of RIS Technology

- Surfaces comprised of hundreds or thousands of simple and ultra-low power circuitry elements with reconfigurable properties.
- Coat objects in the signal propagation environment, such as walls, mirrors, ceilings, or appliances.
- Anomalous reflector of impinging radio waves or as an analog processor of multipath scattering.
- Potentially play the role of a transmitter/ receiver/ sensor when equipped with relevant active radio-frequency elements.
- Supports a wide variety of functionalities:
 - Beamforming
 - Range/position estimation
 - Radio-frequency mapping/sensing
 - Obstacles/activity detection
 - Scattering enrichment
- Particularly suitable for:
 - Limiting EMF exposure.
 - Controlling wave propagation and channel geometry.
 - Reducing the transmission power at existing base stations and access points.

RIS Functional Elements

- **RIS (device):** reflect-array or meta-material directly controlled by an associated RIS actuator.
 - Expected time granularity between 100 microseconds and 10 ms.
- **RIS actuator (RISA):** in charge of actuating the logical commands received from a RISC, translating them into RIS configurations such as phase shifts or ad-hoc meta-material state changes.
 - Can provide feedback or limited sensing to the RISC.
 - Controlled by the RISC with an action time granularity between 1 and 20 ms.
- **RIS controller (RISC):** controls the RIS actuator with logical commands associated to the switching operations between the configurations/states of the RIS elements (e.g., predefined phase shifts).
 - RISC may have different levels of complexity and capabilities and can embed third-party apps to implement smart algorithms.
 - Can be controlled by other elements in the network (Controlled RIS), or operate on its own (Autonomous RIS). The expected action time granularity is between 20 ms and 100 ms.
- **RIS orchestrator (RISO):** placed on a higher (hierarchical) layer and orchestrates multiple RISCs. Action time granularity is expected to be between 100 ms and a few seconds.

RISE Hardware Category and Control Channel Taxonomy

Hardware category	General definition	Capabilities
nearly-passive	No RF chains, only ultra-low-power elements to change the reflection states.	Changing the reflection state of RIS elements.
hybrid	No RF chains, limited sensing capabilities.	Changing the reflection state of RIS elements (like nearly-passive RIS) but with an additional limited sensing capabilities to detect (Tx/Rx) signal Angle-of-Arrival. This might be used for self-configuration and extended to many different use cases.
quasi-active	RF receiving chains are included in the RIS.	Changing the reflection state of RIS elements; it can also collect measurements in baseband for performing sensing/parameters estimation (in time-orthogonal manner with reflection or simultaneously); it can also have processing capabilities to perform localization, channel estimation, etc.
active	RF transmitting chains are included in the RIS.	Changing the reflection state of its elements; it can also perform reflection amplification or transmit its own signals.

Implicit CC		There is no dedicated CC or signal over which explicit instructions are sent to the RISC (but the synchronization signal). As such, all decisions wrt. RIS(A) operations must be made locally by the RISC; however, these decisions can be based on other received and interpreted signals (e.g. pilot symbols, user equipment (UE) scheduling information) which implicitly (indirectly) control the behavior of the RIS.
Explicit CC	Out-of-band	Any communication channel, either wireless or wired, that does not consume resources from the primary communication channel that is influenced by the RIS; examples include: wired channel, wireless channel in a different frequency band, free-space optical, etc. This allows for simpler CC design, but at the cost of possibly lower spectral efficiency.
	In-band	The CC employs resources overlapping RIS operational spectrum resources, so it does influence the operation of the RIS. This implies a more complex CC design, but with possibly higher spectral efficiency.

Sustainable RIS Solutions for EE, EMFEU and SSE

Legend:

EE: Energy-Efficiency
 EMFEU: Electromagnetic-Field Exposure Utility
 SSE: Secrecy Spectral Efficiency

D.-T. Phan Huy, N. Awarkeh, R. Ibrahim, P. Ratajczak, Y. Yu, M. Di Renzo, G. Gradoni, G. Tanner, L. Bastianelli, E. Colella, V. Mariani Primiani, E. Calvanese Strinati, F.-E. Fairold, H. Guo, T. Svensson, R. Kotaba, P. Popovski, G. C. Alexandropoulos, K. D. Katsanos, EU H2020-ICT-2020-2-101017011 RISE-6G, D6.2 "Sustainable RIS solutions design for EE, EMFEU and SSE (Intermediary Specifications)", June 2022

Ongoing RIS Research at Chalmers in the Wireless Systems Team

- RIS-EMFE optimization
- RIS for Internet of Vehicles, IoV (C-V2X)
- D-MIMO and RIS joint optimization
- RIS-aided Integrated Access Backhaul (IAB)
- RIS-empowered Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA)
 - Including also transmissive RIS
- End-to-end (BS-RIS-UE) channel estimation using deep learning
- Context (RF digital twinning) and RIS-aided communications

[1] Y. Liu, et al., "STAR: Simultaneous Transmission And Reflection for 360° Coverage by Intelligent Surfaces", submitted to *IEEE Commun. Mag.*

RIS-EMFE optimization: System Model

Same beam for NIU and IU

Assumptions:

1. NIU consume no power/ blockage effect
2. NIU is a probe to measure the EMF strength

H. Guo, D. -T. Phan-Huy, and T. Svensson, "Electromagnetic Field Exposure Avoidance thanks to Non-Intended User Equipment and RIS," IEEE GLOBECOM Workshop, Dec 2022.

Selected Results

The impact of the EMFE constraint decreases with curves moving right, i.e., IU getting far

- Increasingly better to use the **direct** link with less EMF constraint
- DFT and AO reach similar performance
- Method 3 and 4 reach similar performance (fill in the direct link first vs. exhaustive)

Context-aided Communications: RIS in IoV with Predictor Antenna (PA)

- Potentials and challenges of RIS-based IoV communications in highways with **dynamic blockage pre-avoidance**
- A large-scale fading-based **service region prediction** scheme to reduce the CSIT overhead, together with PA
- The **hardware aspects** of RIS system are also studied

[1] H. Guo, B. Makki, M. Åström, M.-S. Alouini, and T. Svensson, "Dynamic blockage pre-avoidance using reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," submitted to IEEE Communications Magazine, 2022.

Selected Results

We propose a large-scale based RIS pre-assignment (LSRPA) with alternative methods:

1. The proposed LSRPA scheme can obtain the same performance compared to the exhaustive method with full configuration (benchmark), but low overhead
2. Additional BS and network controlled repeater outperforms RIS-based method, but more costly
3. Transceiver impairments and random phase could affect the performance remarkably

Take Home Messages

- Research towards 6G is ongoing
 - 6G aims to address societal needs
- Cell-free Large D-MIMO systems have strong potential
 - both at low (cm/lower mm-wave) and high frequency bands (upper mm-wave)
- RIS technology has potential, but also some remaining challenges
- ML/AI techniques will play an important role
- Convergence of communications and sensing
- Convergence of computing, communications, storage and AI

Still plenty of research to be made!

Hexa-X-II overview

- Hexa-X-II is the next European level 6G Flagship
- Focus will be continued development of technology and define the 6G platform and system
- Funded through Horizon Europe SNS-JU
- 44 partners
 - Cover the entire value-stack from hardware to system to platform to applications to service providers and a strong academic presence
- Nokia is overall leader
- Ericsson is technical manager

EUCNC | 6G Summit

Gothenburg, Sweden ■ 6-9 June 2023

6G for a Green and Digital Transition

www.eucnc.eu

Univ. Chalmers, SE
Local Organiser and
TPC Chair

Univ. Chalmers, SE
Local Organiser
Co-Chair

Upcoming Key Dates

Jan. 2 2023

Open submission of Papers for Regular Sessions, Workshops proposals, Special Sessions proposals, Tutorials proposals, Exhibitions proposals and Travel Grant Applications

Feb. 10 2023 Deadline for submission of Workshops proposals, Special Sessions proposals, and Tutorials proposals, Travel Grant applications

Feb. 19 2023

Deadline for submission of Papers for Regular Sessions

Feb. 13 2023

Open submission of Extended Abstracts for Posters

Mar. 17 2023

Deadline for submission of Extended Abstracts for Posters

Mar. 31 2023 Deadline for submission of proposals for Exhibitions

Apr. 14 2023

Deadline for submission of the final version of the Paper for Regular Sessions, the Extended Abstract for Posters, the Paper for Special Sessions, and the Paper for Workshops, 2023

Apr. 14 2023

Deadline for submission of SME Booth proposals

Apr. 21 2023

Deadline for Registration of Authors (Papers in Regular Sessions and Poster Sessions)

Apr. 28 2023

Tutorial presentations submission

May. 12 2023

Programme available

Jun. 6-9 2023

Conference

Thanks for listening!

Questions?

Tommy Svensson
Prof. Chalmers

Chao Fang
PhD student

Charitha Madapatha
PhD student

Azadeh Tabeshnezhad
PhD student

Mehdi Sattari
PhD student

Hao Guo
Postdoc

Han Yu
Postdoc

N.N.
New postdoc

Behrooz Makki
Senior researcher, Ericsson